

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
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AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN THE FORMATION OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT INDICATORS IN CHILDREN OF MIDDLE SCHOOL AGE**Irbutaeva L.T., Isomiddinov U.X.**

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Resume. *The physical development of children between the ages of 10 and 14 is a period of intense growth and change. Every child is unique. During this age, muscles and bones become stronger. Children can develop greater motor coordination and physical agility. This is the time when many children begin playing sports or actively participating in team sports. It is important to choose a sport that is right for the individual child. A child should enjoy the sport to be motivated and continue to develop. Although the physical development of children who do not participate in sports is well documented, a comprehensive understanding of the development of adolescent athletes, including the potential effects of team sports participation and training load, is lacking.*

Keywords: *sport, children, team sports, advantage, training load.*

ЎРТА МАКТАБ ЁШИДАГИ БОЛАЛАРНИНГ ЖИСМОНИЙ РИВОЖЛАНИШ КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШДА ҲАРАКАТ ФАОЛИЯТИНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ**Ирбутаева Л.Т., Исомиддинов У.Х.**

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Резюме. *10–14 ёшдаги болаларнинг жисмоний ривожланиши жадал ўсиши ва танадаги сезиларли ўзгаришлар билан тавсифланади. Бу даврда ҳар бир бола индивидуал равишда ривожланади, мушаклари ва суяк тизими аста-секин мустаҳкамланади. Шу билан бирга, ҳаракатни мувофиқлаштириши қобилиятлари ва жисмоний чаққонлик ривожланади. Айнан шу ёшда кўплаб болалар спорт билан, жумладан жамоавий спорт турлари билан фаол шугуллана бошлайдилар, бу эса жисмоний ва ижтимоий кўникмаларни янада ривожлантиришига ёрдам беради. Спорт турини танлашда боланинг индивидуал хусусиятларини ҳисобга олиши зарур: машгулотлар мотивацияни сақлаб қолиши ва кейинги ривожланишига ёрдам бериши учун туртки бериши керак. Шу тарзда спорт фаолияти болаларнинг соғлом ўсиши ва ҳар томонлама камол топишига хизмат қилади. Спорт машгулотларига жалб этилмаган болаларнинг жисмоний ривожланиши етарлича батафсил ўрганилган бўлса-да, ўсмир спортчиларнинг ривожланиши жараёнларини ҳар томонлама тушуниши етарли эмас.*

Калим сўзлар: *спорт, болалар, жамоавий спорт турлари, афзаллик, машгулот юки.*

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ДВИГАТЕЛЬНОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ДЕТЕЙ СРЕДНЕГО ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА**Ирбутаева Л.Т., Исомиддинов У.Х.**

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Резюме. *Физическое развитие детей в возрасте 10–14 лет характеризуется интенсивным ростом и значительными изменениями в организме. В этот период каждый ребёнок развивается индивидуально, а мышцы и костная система постепенно укрепляются. Одновременно формируются навыки координации движений и физическая ловкость. Именно в этом возрасте многие дети начинают активно заниматься спортом, включая участие в командных видах, что способствует дальнейшему развитию физических и социальных качеств. При выборе вида спорта необходимо учитывать индивидуальные особенности ребёнка: занятия должны приносить удовольствие, чтобы поддерживать мотивацию и способствовать дальнейшему развитию. Несмотря на то что физическое развитие детей, не вовлечённых в спортивную деятельность, изучено достаточно подробно, отсутствует комплексное понимание процессов развития подростков спортсменов.*

Ключевые слова: *спорт, дети, командные виды спорта, преимущество, тренировочная нагрузка.*

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Every child develops individually, and the rate of their physical development can vary significantly. Regular exercise, a balanced diet, and adequate rest play a key role in maintaining and strengthening the physical development of adolescents involved in team sports.

Team sports are characterized by repeated efforts ranging from low to maximum intensity. Therefore, athletes must be able to accumulate significant reserves of strength and power to perform jumps, sprints, accelerations, changes of direction, and abrupt technical actions such as punches and throws. Research confirms that elite players demonstrate superiority over their competitors in a number of physical parameters. Given the ever-increasing physical demands of modern sports, it is crucial that athletes possess highly developed physical attributes to ensure outstanding results and sustainable career development. This is why the level of physical qualities is considered one of the key criteria for selection into training programs for the best players in team sports.

Understanding the typical trends in physical performance during adolescence is crucial for ensuring the long-term development of adolescent athletes. This information allows for effective progress monitoring, identification of strengths and weaknesses, optimization of training programs, and evaluation of the effectiveness of training interventions. A deeper understanding of the factors influencing development facilitates individualization of training and increases its effectiveness. During this period, growth and overall development of the body are not the primary factors determining the dynamics of physical performance. Instead, key roles are played by processes such as increased body weight and height, muscle fiber differentiation, resting adenosine triphosphate and creatine phosphate levels, increased androgen concentrations, and architectural changes in the musculotendinous system. All of these mechanisms contribute to the development of various physical traits. However, the impact of training load on these processes in children of this age group remains poorly understood and requires further research. Adaptation to training loads in adults has been extensively studied both in the context of physical performance development and injury prevention. However, the unique responses of young athletes to training stimuli remain understudied, highlighting the need for further scientific research in this area. Despite extensive data on boys' physical performance during adolescence, a systematic review that comprehensively summarizes the literature on team sports athletes and includes both boys and girls is currently lacking. This knowledge gap is significant, given that studies of children not involved in sports consistently demonstrate significant developmental differences between the sexes in early and late adolescence.

Results from studies among children who do not participate in sports indicate that boys tend to show greater improvement in physical performance during adolescence, while girls often achieve their best performance soon after puberty, typically between the ages of 13 and 15. These differences may be explained, among other things, by the longer and more powerful developmental and maturational processes that influence boys' physical development. However, it remains unclear whether these patterns hold true for athletes participating in team sports. If team sports athletes follow similar developmental trajectories, their natural development may slow in late adolescence. This may highlight the need for a more targeted physical training program to adequately prepare them for the demands of senior competition. Therefore, the primary objective of this systematic review was to examine the development of physical performance during adolescence in both male and female team sport athletes.

The impact of training load on the development of physical performance was also examined. Two primary reviewers independently assessed the conditions using the "Quality Assessment Tool for Observational Cohort and Cross-Sectional Studies" developed by the National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute. (NHLB, 2021). During the study selection and analysis process, some questions were modified, while others were excluded due to their irrelevance. Any discrepancies or conflicts were resolved through discussion or, if agreement could not be reached, by involving a third reviewer. Because the review included both cross-sectional and longitudinal studies, it should be noted that certain questions (e.g., 7 and 13) pertained exclusively to longitudinal designs. This difference resulted in a potential score of up to seven points for cross-sectional studies and up to nine points for longitudinal studies. All data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and presented as year-over-year differences between age groups. The following tests for each physical characteristic were selected for analysis because they are the most commonly used:

- Sprint: 10 and 30 m.
- Vertical jump: jump against the direction of movement.
- Intermittent Endurance; YYIR tests are a simple method of testing an athlete's ability to perform repeated high-intensity exercise and a multi-stage 20m test.
- Ability to change direction: agility - shuttle run 10 x 5 m and shuttle run 5 x 10 m.
- Upper body strength: grip.

• Lower body strength: the large variety of lower body strength tests in the included studies led to the need to include several different tests. Interestingly, although non-athletic girls typically show a decline in maximal exercise oxygen consumption rate (VO₂ max) around age 14–15, one study found that intermittent endurance performance continues to improve until age 16, just as in boys. This is consistent with the observations made by Tonnessen et al. [2015], who reported improvements in girls' 800m athletics performance even before the age of 18. Differences in results may be due to the characteristics of the tests used. A recent study by Landgraff et al. showed that during adolescence, there was a divergence between maximal oxygen consumption rate (VO₂max) and endurance performance: performance continued to improve, while VO₂max values during exercise remained unchanged.

Given that the multi-stage tests analyzed in this review are performance-based (ie, dependent on multiple physical measures), this may help explain the observed difference between VO₂-max development in non-athlete children and endurance athletes in this review. This means that performance is influenced not only by VO₂-max, but also by other factors, such as specific muscle adaptations that may be more responsive to training. Thus, performance levels are influenced not only by VO₂max values, but also by additional factors, including specific adaptations of the muscular system, which may be more responsive to training stimuli. This review found gradual improvements in most physical performance indicators in adolescents participating in team sports, both in girls and boys, largely related to growth and development. While development is stable and rapid during early adolescence, it appears to slow down by late adolescence. Girls develop more slowly than boys, which may be explained by differences in maturation between the sexes, with boys benefiting more from greater increases in testosterone and limb length. Although the groups in this review were structured by chronological age, examining development based on biological age could add interesting information to better understand the role of maturation in the physical development of adolescent athletes. Future research is encouraged to include maturity measures to provide a more accurate understanding of the impact of changes in the evolution of physical performance in team sport athletes. Because research on the impact of training load and team sport participation on long-term physical development is limited, it is difficult to definitively establish their impact during this period.

To improve our understanding of this topic, future studies should include different measures of training load when examining changes in physical performance in adolescent team sport athletes.

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